

A Comparative Study Based on Time Series and Machine Learning Approaches to Forecast National Currency Exchange Rate of Pakistan

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Abstract

The exchange rate is crucial because it can influence a country economy. It helps brokers and traders make informed operational decisions that reduce risk and maximize profits. Several methods exist for forecasting currency exchange rates. The present study focused on various methodologies, including Box-Jenkins, Holt's method, artificial neural networks, the Facebook Prophet Model, and the Multi-layer Perceptron, for predicting exchange rates. The performance of these techniques is evaluated based on small mean squared error, mean absolute error, and mean absolute percentage error. The results revealed that MLP outperformed all the models. It is a promising method for forecasting the exchange rate of Pakistan, as it yields a relatively minor forecast error. Additionally, the predicted values obtained using MLP are very close to the actual values. The experimental results and time series plot revealed that the exchange rate of Pakistan is expected to increase in the upcoming years. It is concluded that the present study will help to determine the aggregate demand for domestic currency in the coming years. It is also helpful for the government and policymakers. However, understanding exchange rates is essential for anyone involved in international business and finance.

Keywords: Exchange Rate, Machine Learning, Classical Time Series, Forecasting, National Currency

JEL Classification: F31, C45, C53, C22, E37

1. Introduction

The concept of an exchange rate can be explained through economic phenomena such as trade imbalances, price dynamics, trade flows, and current account balances. The importance of the exchange rate has been widely discussed in the literature due to its significant role in promoting economic growth and enhancing international acceptance, as noted by Lane and Milesi-Ferretti (2002). The exchange rate is an essential term that plays a vital role in determining a country's external position. The actual exchange rates have a positive impact on tradable goods and can contribute to economic growth. The value of a country's currency plays a crucial role in determining its economic prosperity, as it affects factors such as trade, investment, and domestic production. Furthermore, improved economic growth and increased domestic production are key factors in determining a country's overall prosperity. The increase in output indicates the attainment of expected revenues. Moreover, the revenue growth stimulates the demand for the local currency. However, as imports increase, the demand for foreign currency also rises, leading to a depreciation in the value of the national currency. The demand for foreign currency also increases due to an expansion in imports, which leads to a decline in the value of the domestic currency. Conversely, maintaining stability in exchange rates leads to an increase in foreign investment, enhanced exports, and a positive shift in the country's trade balance. The exchange rate of a country serves as a benchmark to assess its economic standing in the global arena and to enhance its internal economic stability. A stable exchange rate fosters an environment conducive to increased foreign investment. Additionally, it can lead to higher levels of exports and contribute to a more favorable trade balance for the country. For more details, see Vochozka et al. (2022); Rowland et al. (2021); Bartoš et al. (2022) and the reference cited therein. Depreciation and appreciation are terms used to describe changes in the value of a currency relative to other currencies in the foreign exchange market. Depreciation refers to a decrease in the value of the currency relative to other currencies. On the other hand, appreciation refers to an increase in the value of a currency relative to other currencies. Depreciation can occur due to factors such as inflation, economic downturn, decreased demand for exports, or market speculation. Appreciation can occur due to factors such as economic growth, increased demand for exports, higher interest rates, or market confidence Yousfani et al. (2025). The fluctuations in the exchange rate trend have adverse effects on a country's trade deficit, leading to increased inflation and decreased investment. The rise

in inflation diminishes the country's ability to compete in the global market, resulting in reduced exports and a decrease in demand for its domestic currency. To mitigate the negative consequences of exchange rate instability, one approach is to prioritize trading with developing countries and engage in mutual trade using their respective currencies, rather than relying heavily on foreign currencies. For further insights and comprehensive information, it is recommended to refer to the works of Khan et al. (2014) and the references cited therein.

The current study is being conducted to forecast Pakistan's national currency exchange rate using various methodologies, including Box-Jenkins, Holt's method, Artificial Neural Network (ANN), and Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP). However, research has revealed conflicting views on the relative performance and superiority of Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), Double Exponential Smoothing (DES), and ANN models to time series prediction, particularly for different data sets. This paper aims to clarify the divergent views in the literature concerning whether an ANN with MLP is superior to ARIMA and Double ES methods for accurately predicting national currency exchange rates. The objective of this study is to forecast the exchange rate of the Pakistani currency. However, if it is expected to rise in the coming years, policymakers and the government can implement various measures to address the situation. It is important to note that the specific actions taken by policymakers and the government would depend on the prevailing economic conditions, policy objectives, and available policy tools.

Ref Meyler et al. (1998) created a forecasting framework. They examined the conventional Box-Jenkins method, which can be somewhat subjective, and the objective penalty function criterion as two methods for detecting ARIMA models. De Gooijer and Hyndman (2006) reviewed the previous 25 years of time series forecasting research and concluded that a good forecasting method predicts accurate and timely data. If a forecast can be obtained accurately and on time, it will result in a more precise prediction. To get a more accurate prediction, you must first select a suitable forecast. Erdogdu (2010) focused on demand characteristics. ARIMA models are used to forecast the short and long-run price and income elasticity of Turkey's sectoral natural gas demand. For trend, Kalekar (2004) investigated the use of the DES approach, two components—level and trend—must be adjusted in this approach, which is comparable to basic smoothing in that regard. By determining the average price of sugar in seven traditional marketplaces in Depok from 2014 to 2016, Fauziah et al. (2017) compared the DES and ANN techniques. The ANN technique was shown to be more suitable for predicting the typical price of sugar. Hamid and Abushaba (2020) used the DES and Box-Jenkins techniques to forecast cement output in Sudan. Similar to this, Hansen et al. (1999) examined the performance of ANNs and ARIMA in forecasting time series, concluding that ANNs performed better than ARIMA in predicting the direction of stock movement, as the latter could identify hidden patterns in the data used. A hybrid model proposed by Zhang (2003), which combines both ARIMA and ANN models, leverages the unique advantages of each model in both linear and nonlinear modeling. The outcomes demonstrate that, in terms of predicting accuracy, the combined model beats any of the separate models. For more details, see Munyao et al. (2025); Qureshi et al. (2025) and the references cited therein. According to Iftikhar et al. (2024), the computational strengths of numerous artificial intelligence schemes have been demonstrated to be a valuable tool in providing new and effective ways of addressing a variety of existing and emerging challenges.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents methodology, Section 3 presents results and interpretations, section 4 comprises on discussions and lastly, Section 5 concludes the study by summarizing the main findings.

2. Methods and Material

This paper analyzes and forecasts the time series data using Box-Jenkins Methodology, Holt's ES, and ANN models/algorithms. In this study, we have used data related to Pakistan's exchange rate and forecast it for the next five years. The dataset is sourced from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAOSTAT). This dataset is available at <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/data/PE>. The dataset contained 698 observations from November 2022 to November 2023.

2.1 ARIMA

Box-Jenkins methodology (ARIMA) depends on autoregressive, integrated (difference), and moving average models. In this methodology, non-stationary data can only be used once stationarity is achieved. After estimating the model's parameters, diagnostic checks should be performed. If the model is appropriate after diagnostic checking, forecasts are made; alternative models should be

considered Box and Jenkins (1990). A process X_t is said to follow an ARIMA(p,d,q) model if

$$[\varphi(B)(1 - B)]^d X_t = \theta(B)Z_t, \quad Z_t \sim N(0, \sigma^2), \quad (1)$$

where φ and θ are AR(p) and MA(q) parameters. The residuals are denoted as Z_t . It is independently and identically normally distributed (IIDN).

2.2 Holt's Exponential Smoothing

Holt's double exponential smoothing method, also known as DES, extends simple exponential smoothing to forecast time series data with a trend. This method uses two parameters: the smoothing constant for level ($0 < \alpha < 1$) and the smoothing constant for trend ($0 < \beta < 1$). The three equations of Holt's method are as follows.

The exponentially smoothed series (current level estimate):

$$L_t = \alpha X_t + (1 - \alpha)(L_{t-1} + T_{t-1}) \quad (2)$$

The trend estimate:

$$T_t = \beta(L_t - L_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta)T_{t-1} \quad (3)$$

The forecast for p periods into the future:

$$\hat{X}_{t+p} = L_t + pT_t \quad (4)$$

Where L_t is the new smoothed value, T_t is the trend estimate, p is the number of periods ahead, and \hat{X}_{t+p} is the forecast.

2.3 Artificial Neural Network

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), also known simply as neural networks, are powerful soft computing techniques widely applied in engineering, economics, business, finance, social sciences, and especially forecasting (see Khashei et al. (2009); Khashei and Bijari (2010)). An ANN typically consists of an input layer, a hidden layer(s), and an output layer. The mathematical form of an ANN is given by:

$$M_j = \left(\sum_{k=1}^{j-1} X_k^{(j-1)} W_{k,j} - b_k \right) \quad (5)$$

where $X_k^{(j-1)}$ is the input from the k th node of the $(j - 1)$ th layer, $W_{k,j}$ is the weight of the link, and b_k is the bias term.

The output of the node is:

$$Y_i = f(M_i)$$

where the sigmoid activation function is defined as:

$$f(M_i) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-M_i}} \quad (6)$$

2.4 Multi-layer Perceptron

A Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) is a deep learning architecture consisting of multiple layers of interconnected neurons. It is widely used for supervised learning tasks such as classification and regression. The MLP can model complex nonlinear patterns and extract detailed feature relationships from input data.

Mathematically, the MLP signal processing is expressed as:

$$X_i = f_s \left(\sum_{k=0}^K W_{1,k}^0 \left(f \left(\sum_{n=0}^N W_{kn}^i U_n + b_n \right) \right) \right) \quad (8)$$

2.5 The Facebook Prophet Model

Prophet, developed by Facebook's Data Science Team Vishwas and Patel (2020), is designed for time series data with strong seasonal patterns and several years of historical observations. Prophet is robust to outliers, missing data, and trend shifts. It uses a decomposable time series structure with three key components: trend, seasonality, and holidays.

$$y_t = g_t + s_t + h_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (9)$$

where: - ε_t is the error term capturing unpredictable variations, - h_t represents holiday effects, - s_t denotes seasonal components, - g_t represents the long-term trend.

Prophet fits both linear and nonlinear functions of time using time as a regressor to model these components.

2.6 Error Matrices

Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Square Error (MSE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) are a few of the metrics used to compare performance and select the optimal approach among the underlying algorithms. In this paper, the model's performance is assessed using each of these criteria. These models can be expressed mathematically by the following equations.

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{n=1}^{N_t} (d_n - y_n)^2 \quad (10)$$

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{n=1}^{N_t} |d_n - y_n| \quad (11)$$

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{100}{N_t} \sum_{n=1}^{N_t} \left| \frac{d_n - y_n}{d_n} \right| \quad (12)$$

3. Results

This section begins by visualizing the histogram of exchange rate in Pakistan. Figure 1 illustrates the time series plots of the exchange rate in Pakistan at the level. Firstly, the plot at a glance indicates an upward trend, which suggests that the data is not stationary. Therefore, to eliminate the trend and to make the series stationary, the difference is required. The stationarity of the data has been evaluated using the enhanced Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. The null hypothesis in the ADF test can be defined as the series being non-stationary, while the alternative hypothesis posits that the series is stationary. After 1st difference the series seems stationary and presented in Figure 2. Next this study apply the candidate models using using ARIMA, ES, Facebook Prophet, and NNAR models. The Comparison of different models using MSE, MAE, and MAPE is reported in Table 1.

Figure 1: Time-series plot of Pakistan Exchange rate

Figure 2: Stationary plot of the exchange-rate series after first difference

Table 1: Performance comparison of forecasting models

Model	MSE	MAE	MAPE
ARIMA(2,1,3)	8.3128	1.3628	0.5561
Holt ES	8.5645	1.3786	0.5624
NNAR	15.0459	2.7146	1.0161
MLP	6.8242	1.2282	0.4974
Prophet	40.4647	4.3518	1.7706

From Table 1, it can be seen that the ML algorithm, MLP, is more efficient than the classical Box-Jenkins methodology, ARIMA, as evidenced by all the values of MSE, MAE, and MAPE being lower than those from the ARIMA model. It can also be seen that other ML algorithms, i.e., NNAR and Holt ES, are also close to the ARIMA in terms of the errors as mentioned above. So, in complex univariate time series, the ML-mentioned above algorithms may perform better than the classical Box-Jenkins methodology. The selection and implementation of the appropriate forecast methodology have always been critical planning and control issues for most businesses and government agencies. A monetary policy, specifically in Pakistan, must be controlled to avoid exchange rate instability or to protect exporters from the risk of losing their equity. To reduce the uncertainty of exchange rates, it is necessary for economic development to control or forecast exchange rates. In this study, we forecast Pakistan's exchange rate for the next thirty days using the aforementioned model/algorithms.

Figure 3: Comparative forecast plot utilizing all candidate models

The forecast values of different models are plotted in Figure 3. Figure 3 shows that the forecasting accuracy level of the MLP compared to the ARIMA, Holt ES, and ANN models is significant. It is also observed that the trend pattern of the forecasted values from the MLP model matches the observed values, whereas in other models, such as ARIMA, Holt ES, and ANN, it is directional, i.e., they provide a linear pattern. Therefore, MLP is the most effective method for forecasting Pakistan's national currency exchange rate.

4. Discussion

The results obtained in this study demonstrate that the Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) model achieved the best performance among all the forecasting models used. Specifically, MLP yielded the lowest MSE, MAE, and MAPE values, indicating its superior predictive accuracy. This enhanced performance can be attributed to the MLP's ability to capture complex, nonlinear relationships within the exchange rate data, which traditional models such as ARIMA and Holt's Exponential Smoothing fail to address effectively.

Economically, this result is logical because exchange rate movements in Pakistan are influenced by multiple interacting factors, including inflation, interest rates, fiscal policy, foreign trade, and speculative market behavior. These relationships are rarely linear, and therefore, nonlinear machine learning models like MLP can capture hidden dependencies and nonlinear patterns that linear statistical models overlook. The MLP model can hence provide more realistic and adaptive predictions under volatile economic conditions.

However, it must be acknowledged that the dataset period (November 2022–November 2023) is relatively short for robust long-term forecasting. This short data span limits the model's ability to generalize, particularly when structural changes or external shocks affect the currency. The limitation of a small sample size may also lead to overfitting in complex neural network models, such as MLP. Similarly, while the ARIMA model effectively captured short-term linear dependencies, it was unable to model nonlinear trends. Holt's method performed moderately well but is less flexible in dynamic economic environments. Facebook Prophet, while handling seasonality efficiently, exhibited higher forecast errors due to the limited availability of historical data and irregular economic shocks. The NNAR model performed well, but not as effectively as the MLP, due to its fewer hidden layers and limited feature transformation capabilities Liang et al. (2023); Irfan et al. (2011).

Therefore, the MLP model's superior performance suggests that deep learning-based models have substantial potential for financial forecasting in developing economies such as Pakistan. Future research should consider extending the dataset period, incorporating macroeconomic indicators, and exploring hybrid deep learning models (e.g., LSTM, GRU) to improve predictive reliability and economic interpretability Iftikhar et al. (2024); Nasir et al. (2025).

5. Conclusion

The exchange rate of a country is used to compare its economy at the international level, strengthen internal economic stability, and improve foreign investment. This study investigates the national currency exchange rate of Pakistan using Box–Jenkins, Double Exponential Smoothing, and ANN. The results revealed that ANN performs best because it has the least forecast errors, and its predicted values are very close to the actual values, as shown in Figure 3. Hence, ANN may perform better than classical ARIMA for complex time series data.

Figure 3 clearly shows that the national currency exchange rate of Pakistan is expected to increase in the upcoming years. Exchange rates affect international trade, investment, tourism, central bank policy, and currency risk; therefore, understanding them is essential for international business and finance. The study also helps determine aggregate demand for the domestic currency and is useful for the government and policymakers.

When the exchange rate rises, several measures can stabilize it: (i) adjusting interest rates; (ii) foreign exchange market intervention using reserves; (iii) fiscal policy adjustments; (iv) long-term structural reforms. The choice of measures depends on economic conditions and policy objectives.

Limitations and Future Work

The main limitation of this study is the short data duration from November 2022 to November 2023, which may not capture long-term exchange rate trends. While the MLP model performed well, its accuracy may depend on hyperparameter tuning and data availability. Future studies should use longer datasets and include exogenous macroeconomic variables such as GDP growth, inflation, and interest rate differentials. Advanced deep learning models like LSTM and GRU can also be explored to enhance temporal learning and long-term forecasting accuracy.

Author Contributions

Zairash Rashid: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; Mahwish Rabia: Supervision, Project Administration, Writing – Review & Editing; Zakia Batool: Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Visualization; Humma Nawaz: Software, Validation, Investigation; Amir Raza: Resources, Funding Acquisition, Writing – Review & Editing.

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Data Availability Statement

The dataset is publicly available at the following link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat>

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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